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RESEARCH PAPER

THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF SILYMARIN IN ATTENUATING IRON ORE-INDUCED TESTICULAR TOXICITY

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the protective effects of Silymarin (SIL) in Iron-ore induced testicular toxicity. Forty-four Wistar rats were divided into four groups: control, SIL (20 mg/kg), iron ore (4.5 mg/kg), and SIL + iron ore. Treatments were administered orally for four weeks, after which semen quality, serum testosterone, and testicular antioxidant status, lipid peroxidation, and histology were evaluated. Statistical analysis was conducted, means were compared using one-way ANOVA, with p-values <0.05 considered significant. Iron exposure significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced sperm count (81.6 ± 9.1 vs. $28.3 \pm 3.8 \times 10^6/\text{mL}$), normal morphology ($74.2 \pm 12.3\%$ vs. $52.5 \pm 8.7\%$), and serum testosterone levels (4.9 ± 0.7 vs. 2.2 ± 0.3 ng/mL) compared to control. MDA levels increased (4.5 ± 1.4 vs. 8.4 ± 2.6 nmol/mg tissue), while antioxidant enzyme activities (SOD, CAT, GPx) decreased. SIL co-treatment significantly improved sperm count ($61.7 \pm 6.9 \times 10^6/\text{mL}$), while also increasing, sperm morphology and motility, testosterone. The SIL restored testicular antioxidant levels, and reduced testicular MDA (7.2 ± 2.3 nmol/mg tissue) in Iron-ore rats. Histological analysis showed that SIL mitigated some of the structural damage caused by iron. These findings suggest that SIL mitigates iron ore-induced testicular toxicity by enhancing antioxidant defense and preserving reproductive parameters.

Keywords: Antioxidant, Iron Ore, Infertility, Oxidative Stress, Lipid peroxidation, Silymarin

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a major clinical concern, affecting individuals both medically and psychologically, and is defined by the World Health Organization as the inability to achieve a clinical pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sexual intercourse (Turner *et al.*, 2020). The prevalence of infertility has increased globally, affecting an estimated 50 to 80 million couples during their reproductive years due to various behavioral and biological factors, with about 3 to 4 million couples affected in Nigeria (Obeagu *et al.*, 2023; Orij *et al.*, 2022). This condition poses a major health challenge, with male factors accounting for more than 25% of these cases (Deshpande and Gupta, 2019).

A reduction in fertility rates has been noted, with environmental toxic exposures, such as heavy metals, being linked to this decline (Crocetto *et al.*, 2023). The widespread environmental presence of heavy metals makes exposure common, and these substances have been shown to disrupt the reproductive system (Dutta *et al.*, 2022; Mukherjee *et al.*, 2022). In Nigeria, iron ore deposits are abundant and have played a significant role in the country's industrial development

(Olade, 2019). Iron ore, primarily composed of magnetite and hematite, is an essential raw material in the production of steel, construction materials, and for electroplating and metal galvanization (Cheneket, 2018). However, mining activities not only cause environmental harm but also result in chemical contamination, negatively impacting the health of local populations. Research on iron ore toxicity in animal models has demonstrated that excessive elemental iron can impair renal and hepatic function, disrupt blood coagulation, damage the gastrointestinal mucosa, and cause metabolic and hemodynamic disturbances (Kontoghiorghes, 2023; Lal, 2020; Mueller *et al.*, 2022). Iron ore exposure has been found to impair testicular function and morphology, suggesting a negative impact on male fertility (Nwangwa *et al.*, 2015).

Over the past decade, numerous clinical studies have highlighted the positive effects of antioxidants on sperm parameters in men and improved fertilization or pregnancy rates in their partners (Agarwal *et al.*, 2022; Martin-Hidalgo *et al.*, 2019). The recognition of Silymarin as a natural therapeutic agent, along with its inclusion in clinical trials by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) in the United States, underscores its potential for organoprotection (Jaffar *et al.*, 2024). Silymarin is noted for its antioxidant properties, which mitigate oxidative stress, preserve genomic integrity, and prevent apoptotic and necrotic cell death (Camini and Costa, 2020; Surai, 2023).

In light of increasing concerns regarding the decline in male fertility linked to environmental exposure to heavy metals such as iron ore, there remains a paucity of data on effective therapeutic interventions to counteract the associated testicular toxicity. This study aims to investigate the protective efficacy of silymarin against testicular damage induced by iron ore exposure. The central hypothesis is that silymarin administration will significantly attenuate testicular oxidative stress, improve histological architecture, and restore sperm parameters in iron ore-exposed animal models. The expected measurable outcomes include reductions in oxidative stress biomarkers, improvements in testicular histopathology, and enhancement in sperm count, motility, and morphology.

METHODOLOGY

Drugs/chemicals: Silymarin was obtained from a pharmaceutical store in Benin City, Nigeria, while iron ore pellets were provided by a mining company located in Itakpe, Kogi State, Nigeria. The majority of the reagents were sourced from Finlab in Abuja, Nigeria. All chemicals utilized in the experiments were of analytical grade.

Preparation of silymarin and Iron Ore: Silymarin was dissolved in distilled water, and the maximum amount of the solution administered to the rats was determined based on their body weight, using a reference dose of 20 ml/kg as outlined by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development guidelines (OECD, 2008). Following these guidelines, a concentration of 10 mg/ml of silymarin was prepared to achieve a final dose of 20 mg/kg. The dosage was established based on the lethal dose (LD-50) as outlined by (AL-Fatlawi *et al.*, 2021). Silymarin was administered orally to the rats for a period of 4 weeks. Iron ore, initially in a coarse form, was finely pulverized using a mortar and pestle. Iron ore, originally in coarse form, was pulverized using a mortar and pestle to produce a fine powder. A suspension was then prepared by dispersing 4.5 g of the powdered iron ore in 1 liter of tap water to yield a final dose of 4.5 mg/kg. However, as iron ore is not truly soluble in water, this preparation represents a suspension rather than a true solution. Therefore, the mixture was stirred thoroughly to ensure homogeneity prior to administration.

Experimental Animals: Forty-four (44) male Wistar rats, of approximately 10 – 12 weeks old, were housed in polypropylene cages and maintained under controlled conditions (12-hour light/dark cycles, 25 ± 5 °C) at the Animal House, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Edo State University Iyamho, Nigeria. The rats had unrestricted access to food and drinking water. They were randomly assigned into four (4) groups, each containing eleven (11) rats. The animals underwent a two-week acclimatization period prior to the start of the experiment.

Ethical Consideration: All procedures were conducted in strict accordance with the National Institutes of Health Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (NIH Publications No. 8023, revised 1978), and approval was obtained from the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee before commencing the study (RBC/FBMS/EUI25-149).

Experimental protocol: The animals were divided into four groups: Group I, serving as the normal control, received saline; Group II was administered SIL (20 mg/kg body weight); Group III received Iron Ore (4.5 mg/kg body weight); and Group IV was treated with both SIL and Iron Ore. All experimental treatments were administered orally for four weeks.

Samples collection: At the conclusion of the experiment, the animals were euthanized through cervical dislocation. Semen was collected for analysis, and the testes were excised. Blood samples were obtained via cardiac puncture and collected into plain containers for serum hormonal assays.

Seminal Fluid Analysis: The testes were excised, and the cauda epididymis was identified for semen collection, following a method described by Saba *et al.* (2009). Semen was immediately analyzed for sperm count, progressive motility, and normal morphology. Sperm count was determined using a hemocytometer. The cauda epididymis was minced in normal saline, filtered, and a 10 μ l aliquot was placed on the hemocytometer for counting using the improved Neubauer chamber under a light microscope (Pant & Srivastava, 2003). Progressive sperm motility was assessed as outlined by Kadir *et al.* (2018); semen was placed on a glass slide, treated with 2.9% sodium citrate, stirred, covered with a glass slip, and then examined under a light microscope to differentiate motile from non-motile sperm. For sperm morphology, 400 spermatozoa were examined after placing the semen on a slide and adding Wells and Awa stains (composed of 0.2g eosin and 0.6g fast green in distilled water and ethanol, in a 2:1 ratio), as described by Adedara *et al.* (2018). The stained semen was then observed under the microscope.

Serum testosterone analysis: Blood samples were obtained via cardiac puncture at a consistent time each day to reduce diurnal variation. The samples were collected into plain containers, and serum was separated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. The serum was then stored at -70°C until further analysis. Serum testosterone levels were determined using the double-antibody radioimmunoassay method (Coat-A-Count).

Evaluation of Antioxidant Enzymes and Lipid Peroxidation: The testis tissue was immediately excised, and a portion was thawed and manually homogenized in cold phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). After centrifugation at 3500 g for 10 minutes (Centrifuge 5415 R; Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany), the supernatants were collected for the analysis of malondialdehyde (MDA), superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) levels. SOD activity was assessed following Fridovich (1975) by diluting 0.1 ml of serum in 0.9 ml distilled water, then mixing 0.2 ml of the diluted microsome with 2.5 ml of 0.05M carbonate buffer and initiating the reaction with 0.3 ml of 0.3 mM adrenaline. Absorbance was measured at 480 nm over 30-150 seconds. CAT activity was measured using Aebi (1984) technique, where 10 μ l of serum was added to 2.8 ml of 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer, and the reaction was initiated with 0.1 ml of freshly prepared 30 mM H₂O₂, with the decomposition rate measured at 240 nm for 5 minutes. GPx activity was determined using Ellman (1959) method, where 0.5 ml of serum was precipitated with 2 ml of 5% trichloroacetic acid, followed by the addition of Ellman's reagent and phosphate buffer, and the color developed was read at 412 nm. MDA concentration in the testicular tissue was measured according to Aliyu *et al.* (2017) by treating 0.1 ml of serum with a reagent mixture of tert-butyl alcohol, trichloroacetic acid, and hydrochloric acid, incubating in a water bath for 15 minutes, then cooling, centrifuging, and measuring the clear supernatant at 535 nm.

Histopathological preparations of the testis: Testicular tissues were fixed in Bouin's fluid and processed according to standard procedures and embedded in paraffin wax. Thin sections were cut, stained with hematoxylin and eosin (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), dehydrated, and mounted. Images were captured using a 400 \times objective lens under a light microscope.

Statistical analysis: Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess mean differences among the groups, followed by the Least Significant Difference (LSD) post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Prior to performing

ANOVA, assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance were assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test and Levene’s test, respectively. A power calculation was conducted using G*Power software to ensure adequate sample size for detecting a medium effect size ($f = 0.25$) with 73% power at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. To reduce bias, blinding was implemented during both histological evaluations and data analysis.

RESULTS

Effects of SIL on Semen Quality and serum Testosterone level of rats treated with Iron Ore.

Sperm count, progressive sperm motility, normal sperm morphology, and serum testosterone levels were evaluated. Rats in the Iron Ore-treated group showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in sperm count ($28.3 \pm 3.8 \times 10^6/\text{ml}$), normal sperm morphology ($52.5 \pm 8.7\%$), and serum testosterone levels ($2.2 \pm 0.3 \text{ ng/ml}$) compared to the normal control group ($81.6 \pm 9.1 \times 10^6/\text{ml}$, $74.2 \pm 12.3\%$, and $4.9 \pm 0.7 \text{ ng/ml}$, respectively) and the Silymarin-only group ($85.0 \pm 9.1 \times 10^6/\text{ml}$, $81.2 \pm 12.0\%$, and $4.8 \pm 0.7 \text{ ng/ml}$, respectively). A significant ($p < 0.05$) decline in progressive sperm motility ($54.1 \pm 7.7\%$) was also observed in Iron Ore-treated rats when compared to the normal group ($72.5 \pm 10.4\%$). Co-administration of Silymarin improved semen quality for normal sperm morphology and progressive motility ($64.5 \pm 11.0\%$, and $62.6 \pm 9.1\%$), and serum testosterone levels ($3.4 \pm 0.4 \text{ ng/ml}$) in Iron Ore-treated rats, mitigating the effects of iron toxicity. However, the improvement was only statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) for sperm count ($61.7 \pm 6.9 \times 10^6/\text{ml}$) compared to the Iron Ore-only group (Fig. 1A).

Fig. 1: (A) Sperm count (B) Progressive Sperm Motility (C) Normal Sperm Morphology (D) Testosterone after Silymarin (SIL) administration in Iron Ore (Fe-Ore)-treated rats. Data are represented as means \pm SD ($n = 11$). * $p < 0.05$ compared to control group, # $p < 0.05$ compared to SIL group, b < 0.05 compared to Iron Ore (2-column fitting image)

Effects of SIL on Testicular Oxidative Stress Status of rats treated with Iron Ore

Figure 2 illustrates the changes in testicular antioxidant levels—superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx)—as well as the lipid peroxidation marker malondialdehyde (MDA). In the Iron Ore-treated group, there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in testicular antioxidant levels: SOD (3.6 ± 0.4 U/mgHb), CAT (4.0 ± 0.5 U/mgHb), and GPx (0.2 ± 0.1 U/mgHb) compared to the normal control group: SOD (7.0 ± 1.7 U/mgHb), CAT (7.2 ± 0.9 U/mgHb), and GPx (0.5 ± 0.2 U/mgHb), as well as the SIL-only group: SOD (7.4 ± 0.9 U/mgHb), CAT (8.4 ± 1.1 U/mgHb), and GPx (0.8 ± 0.2 U/mgHb). Conversely, MDA levels significantly increased (8.4 ± 2.6 nmol/mg tissue) in the Iron Ore group compared to the normal (4.5 ± 1.4 nmol/mg tissue) and SIL-only (3.9 ± 1.2 nmol/mg tissue) groups ($p < 0.05$). Treatment with Silymarin significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated antioxidant enzyme levels in Iron Ore-exposed rats: SOD (4.9 ± 0.6 U/mgHb), CAT (5.4 ± 0.6 U/mgHb), and GPx (0.8 ± 0.1 U/mgHb). Although Silymarin reduced MDA levels in Iron Ore-treated rats (7.2 ± 2.3 nmol/mg tissue), this reduction was not statistically significant compared to the Iron Ore-only group (Fig. 2D).

Fig. 2: (A) Superoxide Dismutase (B) Catalase (C) Glutathione peroxidase (D) Malonaldehyde after Silymarin (SIL) administration in Iron Ore (Fe-Ore)-treated rats. Data are represented as means \pm SD (n = 11). * $p < 0.05$ compared to control group, # $p < 0.05$ compared to SIL group, ^b $p < 0.05$ compared to Iron Ore (2-column fitting image)

Protective effect of SIL on Histology of testis of rats treated with Iron Ore

The effect of silymarin on the histology of the testes in rats treated with Iron Ore is depicted in Figure 3. In the control group (A), the seminiferous tubules (ST) show a normal structure with clearly defined lumens (L), mature germ cells (GC), and intact interstitium containing interstitial cells (IC), with no signs of inflammation. In contrast, the testicular architecture of rats treated with Iron Ore (C) exhibits significant damage, including degeneration of the seminiferous

tubules (DST), interstitial degeneration (ID), sloughing of the germinal epithelium, and spermatogenic arrest, highlighting the toxic impact of Iron Ore exposure. However, when silymarin was co-administered with Iron Ore, there was a noticeable improvement in testicular histology, although not to the extent of complete restoration. This group showed a reduction in spermatogenesis, fewer germ cells, and mild interstitial damage, but the basement membrane remained intact, indicating that silymarin had a protective effect by mitigating some of the histological alterations induced by Iron Ore exposure.

Fig 3: Histological changes in the testis (H&E staining; X400 magnification): (A) Normal testis (B) SIL treated testis (C) Fe-Ore-treated testis (D) Fe-Ore + SIL-treated. Normal seminiferous tubules (ST), defined lumens (L), mature germ cells (GC), interstitial cells (IC).

DISCUSSION

Environmental pollution from heavy metals poses a significant threat to reproductive health, as these endocrine-disrupting toxins impair fertility by disrupting hormonal balance and reducing gamete quality, with exposure often being unavoidable (Manouchehri *et al.*, 2022). While iron plays a vital role in sustaining ejaculate fluidity and maintaining sperm pH within a functional range—facilitated by ferritin produced by Sertoli and Leydig cells for delivery to developing sperm—excessive accumulation of iron, particularly due to iron ore exposure, has been linked to disruptions in male reproductive function (Gabrielsen *et al.*, 2018).

The findings of this study demonstrated that iron ore administration led to a significant reduction in sperm count, progressive motility, normal morphology, and serum testosterone levels in rats. These observations align with those of (Ammar *et al.*, 2019), who reported that elevated iron concentrations in seminal plasma were linked to teratozoospermia and reduced motility, potentially due to increased reactive oxygen species and subsequent lipid peroxidation. Similarly, Wise *et al.* (2003) noted that high testicular iron levels impair spermatogenesis and directly damage sperm cells. Consistent with this, Nwangwa *et al.* (2015) also documented adverse effects on semen quality in animals exposed to iron ore. The significant reductions in sperm parameters observed in this study may be attributed to disrupted spermatogenesis, likely resulting from iron ore-induced suppression of testicular testosterone secretion. This aligns with the findings of Uitz *et al.* (2013), who suggested that iron overload in the pituitary gland may contribute to reduced testosterone levels.

The histopathological analysis offered deeper insights into the underlying mechanisms of testicular toxicity induced by iron ore exposure. The heavy metal was found to cause degenerative alterations in the seminiferous tubules, including the disruption of spermatogenesis. Damage to the seminiferous epithelium likely contributes to the degeneration of Sertoli and germ cells, thereby impairing spermatogenesis, compromising sperm function, and reducing testosterone levels (Hasan *et al.*, 2022; Houda *et al.*, 2021). Previous studies, including those by Ezzat *et al.* (2023) have documented that iron ore exposure promotes lipid peroxidation, a key driver of oxidative stress, which was corroborated by the present findings showing marked disruption of testicular redox balance. This oxidative disturbance in lipid peroxidation and antioxidant defenses may underlie the suppression of testosterone synthesis and subsequent decline in sperm quality (O’Flaherty & Scarlata, 2022). Furthermore, Knazicka *et al.* (2021) reported that excessive iron can inflict oxidative damage to sperm DNA, thereby impairing spermatogenesis and overall male fertility.

Silymarin (SIL), a flavonolignan compound, is widely recognized for its potent antioxidant and cytoprotective properties, primarily through its ability to scavenge free radicals (Chambers *et al.*, 2019). This study critically supports that assertion, demonstrating that SIL administration led to increases in testicular antioxidants—SOD, CAT, and GPx—in rats exposed to Iron Ore. The observed reduction in MDA levels further substantiates SIL’s capacity to counter lipid peroxidation, a finding consistent with Mirzaei *et al.* (2021) who demonstrated similar effects. These biochemical improvements were mirrored histologically, as SIL notably ameliorated testicular architecture in iron ore-exposed rats, suggesting a restorative impact on oxidative damage. Additionally, the concurrent rise in serum testosterone and enhancement of spermatogenesis in these rats highlights SIL’s potential to improve endocrine and reproductive parameters compromised by toxic exposure. These findings are corroborated by previous studies (El-Ashmawy *et al.*, 2020; Heidari Khoei *et al.*, 2019), which report similar benefits of SIL on male fertility indicators. Moreover, the broader implications of antioxidant therapy in male reproductive health, as discussed by Aqeel-Abdul (2023) and Walke *et al.* (2023), reinforce the mechanistic link between oxidative stress mitigation and functional recovery of Leydig cells and seminiferous tubules—ultimately leading to increased testosterone production and improved spermatogenesis. Taken together, the evidence positions SIL not only as a protective agent but also as a promising therapeutic intervention in the management of heavy metal-induced testicular toxicity.

This study has several limitations. The treatment duration was relatively short, which may have limited the observation of long-term reproductive effects of both iron ore exposure and Silymarin intervention. Second, molecular analyses such as gene or protein expression profiling of oxidative stress and apoptotic markers were not conducted, and direct fertility outcomes such as mating success, pregnancy rate, or litter size were not assessed. While these factors would have provided deeper mechanistic and functional insights, their absence did not affect the reliability of the core findings, which were based on well-established biochemical, hormonal, and histological parameters. The results remain valid within the scope of evaluating testicular toxicity and the protective effects of Silymarin. However, future studies incorporating these additional measures are warranted to strengthen the translational value of the findings.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings of this study indicate that SIL exerts a protective effect against iron ore-induced testicular toxicity by enhancing antioxidant enzyme activity, reducing MDA levels, and preserving both spermatogenic and steroidogenic functions of the testes. This protective capacity is likely attributable to SIL's potent antioxidant properties. Consequently, SIL may hold therapeutic potential for mitigating testicular damage associated with exposure to iron ore and other heavy metals, supporting its prospective application in clinical management of environmentally induced male reproductive dysfunction.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:

Ekhoeye Ehitare Ikekhuamen: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Roles/Writing - original draft. Willy Barinem Vidona: Data collection, Investigation, Resources, Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing - review & editing.

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